

Research Article

Distribution of Hepatitis A Virus Infections with Public Health Impact in Al-Diwanya Province, Iraq

Mohammed Abdulkadhim Sayah^{1*}¹Department of Anatomy, College of Medicine, University of Al-Qadisiyah, Al-Diwanya, Iraq.*Corresponding author: mohammed.abdulkadhim@qu.edu.iq

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Abstract

Aim: Infection with the hepatitis A virus represents one of the very important and prevalent viral infections that associated with food and drinking water contamination, especially in developing countries that suffer from high population density and may be linked to poor sanitation services. Besides, some infections are also linked to lack of personal hygiene care, especially among children. It is necessary to continuously investigate the presence of such infections in different regions and for different ages and genders for the purpose of completely controlling this infection and preventing its spread.

Objective: Iraq represent low to moderate endemic for hepatitis A virus. So, estimation of frequency of hepatitis A virus amongst population of Al-Diwanya province to determining the risk factors that could associated with this infection and working to combat or reduce the spread of such infections for the purpose of protecting society.

Results: A total of 230 participants that suspected of infection with hepatitis A virus, only 66 (28.7%) showed seropositivity for this virus. This infection distributed according to age into four groups as following group A < 5 (27%), group B 5-14 (38%), group C 15-45 (27%), and D > 45 (20%) %, the mean/SD of age was (18.2±21.8). According to sex, the result showed the male rate was (67%) while female rate was (33%). According to residency, the result showed rural areas were (77%) while urban areas showed (23%). However, it was no significant statistically differences between the infection with Hepatitis A virus and age, sex, and residency of patients at ($P < 0.05$).

1. Introduction

Hepatitis can be defined as liver inflammation illness that can be caused by many factors such as immoderate alcohol consumption, autoimmune illnesses, medicines, or pollutants material. However, viral hepatitis regarded as the most frequent form of hepatitis that caused by a virus [1].

Hepatitis viruses include many virus types such as hepatitis A virus (HAV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis E virus (HEV), and hepatitis D virus (HDV), can cause infectious disease and produce liver lesions, which are the major symptom of viral hepatitis [2].

Generally, one the most frequent etiologic factors of acute form of viral hepatitis is HAV infection, which is also a significant global health issue, particularly in developing nations. Globally, it is estimated that 1.5 million people have hepatitis A illnesses yearly [3]. Infection with this contagious virus may lead to severe illness and occasionally to death. However, the presence of the HAV- vaccine has reduced these risks [4].

HAV was first discovered in 1973 and is very small, no-envelope, positive-strand RNA- virus that related to the genus *Hepatovirus* and to family Picornaviridae [5–7].

HAV causes epidemics, sporadic, anicteric, or icteric hepatitis (in both symptomatic and asymptomatic instances), and is mostly transmitted by the fecal-oral route and by consuming contaminated foods and drinks. Early childhood infections are more likely to occur in areas with poor sanitation and socioeconomic situations. However, exposure to saliva or urine does not result in transmission; instead, it happens after exposure to blood or blood products that are contaminated with HAV [8–10].

These particles of HAV are extremely persistent in the typical environment; for example, high infectious load can still be existed on surfaces at room temperature after 60 days of desiccation, in water and soil after some weeks of shedding in the feces which in turn gives it the opportunity to survive effectively in nature and under harsh environmental conditions [11–13].

The only reservoir of HAV that has been identified is humans. generally, HAV infection regarded as self-limited illnesses that does not developed to chronic form disease in severe cases. Less than 1% of HAV infected patients include fulminant hepatic failure [14].

Hepatitis A can have a variety of clinical consequences, from asymptomatic to fulminant hepatitis. Hepatitis A in children often has a significantly more moderate clinical course than in adults; roughly 70% of HAV infections in children remain asymptomatic, compared to an estimated greater than 70% of symptomatic infection rates in adults. A rare complication of hepatitis A known as fulminant hepatitis is thought to be play a substantial role in patient mortality. Acute infection symptoms of HAV- infected patients include fever, nausea, vomiting, lethargy, malaise, stomach discomfort, and a lack of appetite [15, 16].

For detection of HAV infection and differentiate HAV from other hepatitis viruses, the humoral type of immune response is critical. There are some available IgM tests that can be used to identify acute HAV infection. For the purpose of detect HAV RNA. PCR molecular technique that can accurately identify viral genome have the prospect to improve diagnosis of HAV [17, 18].

Supportive care is used in the treatment of acute hepatitis A infection. HAV vaccine is available and regarded as reliable and efficient vaccine [19, 20]. This infection can provide a lifelong immunity against HAV after infection that occurs naturally or after obtaining the vaccine for this virus [21].

2. Material and Methods

This a cross -sectional study was achieved in public health laboratory in Al-Diwanyah province. This study include 230 patients was attended to this laboratory during 2023. The study involved people who have been tested and suspected to infection with hepatitis A virus.

Ethical concerns were addressed. Their demographic status including gender, age, and residency data was recorded and submitted on a pre-made questionnaires. Samples were assembled by venipuncture process; (5 ml) of blood was taken utilizing disposable proper syringes. The blood was put in disposable proper tubes, then remain at room temperature (18-25°C) to be clot. Sera were isolated and kept at -20°C until assayed. Serum filled with anti-HAV antibody (IgG) was diagnosed by Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay technique (ELISA) with Dialab kit.

Statistics

(SPSS version 20) was utilized for statistical analysis. Utilized of the chi-square test for comparing HAV seropositivity by socio-demographic variables. ($P < 0.05$) considered to be significant statistically.

3. Results

Present result showed the percentage of HAV- seropositive patients was 28.6% (66/230) out of all participants that have been tested in public health laboratory in Al-Diwanyah province.

This result was distributed to three categories (age, sex, and residency). According to age, the result divided into four groups that range (< 5 to 45) years which revealed group-B (5-14) years has the highest percentage 25/66(38%), group-A (< 5) was 18/66 (27%), group C (15-44) was 18/66 (27%), and group D was 5/66 (8%). The mean/SD of age was (18.2±21.8). There were no statistically significant variables between age groups of patients at ($P < 0.05$) as mentioned in table 1

Table 1: distribution of anti HAV-IgG amongst age of patients' group

Age group (years)	Suspected	IgG Positive	IgG Negative	Positive %	P-value
A- (< 5)	85	18	67	18/66(27%)	0.2
B-(5-14)	80	25	55	25/66(38%)	
C-(15-45)	40	18	22	18/66(27%)	
D-(> 45)	25	5	20	5/66 (8%)	
Total	230	66	164	100%	

* P-value $P < 0.05$ consider significant variables statistically

Also, according to gender, the result showed that male's group has the highest percentage which constituted 40/66(60%) patients in comparison to female 26/66 (40%). It was no significant varies between residency types of patients at ($P < 0.05$) as mentioned in table 2

Table 2: Distribution of HAV-seropositive patients concerning sex

Characteristics	Suspected	Positive hepatitis no (%)	Residency to seropositive ratio (%)	P-value
Residency				0.1
Urban	75	15 (20%)	15/66(23%)	
Rural	155	51 (33%)	51/66(77%)	
Total	230	66	100%	

*P-value $P < 0.05$ consider significant varies statistically

Besides, according to residency the present study showed that rural group has the highest percentage which constitute 15/66 (23%) patients, while the rural which constitute 51/66 (77%), There was no significant differences between residency of patients at ($P < 0.05$) as mentioned in table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of HAV-seropositive patients concerning residency

Characteristics	Suspected	Positive hepatitis no (%)	Residency to seropositive ratio (%)	P-value
Sex				0.4
Male	135	40/135 (30%)	40/66(60%)	
Female	95	26/135 (27%)	26/66(40%)	
Total	230	66		

*P-value $P < 0.05$ consider significant varies statistically

4. Discussion

The main finding of our result is revealing of HAV-seropositive cases in Al-Diwanyah province with rate around (28.7%) of all suspected cases.

In comparable with other related researches that performed in other regions of Iraq previously, we can see ,the present results were lower than the result of Dohuk province which revealed the prevalence of HAV- patients was 68.3% [22], results of Wasit province that showed 37.6% [23], results of Baquba that showed 73% [24], results of Misan province that showed 73% out of all types of hepatitis infections [25], results of Karbala province that showed 61.7% [26], results of Baghdad province 41% [27], and results of Babylon province that showed 54.3% [28]. On other hand, our result was higher than the result of Mosul province which revealed the prevalence of HAV- patients was 21.7% [29].

Also, based on this study, the higher infection rate among males compared to females may because of male more susceptible to viral infections [30]. This may due to due to several factors, including those males are more numerous and mixed with each other, or it may be due to their lack of care for personal hygiene compared to females. As for the residential area, we notice an increase in infection in rural compared to urban regions, which may be because of contamination of drinking water or lack of proper purification, and low-health awareness which increases the amount of infection [31].

In general, according to our result we can propose that Al-Diwanyah province shows a clear decrease in the rate of infection with this virus compared to the rest of the aforementioned regions of Iraq, and this may indicate the low presence of this virus in drinking water or food, which may indicate the relative cleanliness of river streams and the quality of drinking water in this city.

5. Conclusion

Based on this study, the following conclusions could be made, there was relatively decreasing risk of HAV-infection in Al-Diwanyah province. Age group (5-14) years represented the highest risk age among HAV-patients. Male infection with HAV was higher than female. Rural population have increased risk of HAV infection than urban. Recommendations include performing more tests for detecting and proving the HAV-infections, interesting in popular hygiene activities especially regarding children and adolescent groups and giving a proper treatment of water in order to prevent HAV- transmission among people, support of administration of anti -HAV vaccine for protecting individuals and increasing health awareness among people for protecting them from HAV-infection.

Article Information

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

Competing Interests: Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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